

OPENLAB
ESEV

MWB 2013

11 - 12 April 2013

Innsbruck

[OpenLab ESEV]

a narrative of Libre Software and
Free Culture in a portuguese
higher education institution

Nelson A. F. Gonçalves
School of Education / CI&DETS
Polytechnic Institute of Viseu (Portugal)

Maria P. Figueiredo
School of Education / CI&DETS
Polytechnic Institute of Viseu (Portugal)

[Context and origins]

- ESEV is a public institution of higher education
- founded in 1983 as a teacher education institution
- over 1500 students and 105 teachers, 9 undergraduate and 13 Master's programs (Teacher Ed., Plastic Arts and Multimedia, Media Studies, Cultural Animation, Social Education, Sports and Physical Activity and Environmental Ed.)

Minimum wage = 475€
MS Office 2013 (Student) = 120€

[Context and origins]

OpenLab emerged in 12/2009 because of the **lack of knowledge of the existing Libre alternatives** and **work habits exclusively built around proprietary software.**

(Gonçalves & Figueiredo, 2008).

Teach Ed

1 in 4 Unlicensed OS

Kompozer (32%) - 30% Unlic + DN

OO Writer (11%) - 50% Unlic + DK

Firefox (11%) - 45% Unlic + DN

Arts

1 in 3 Unlicensed OS

Firefox (40%) - 15% Unlic + DK

Software is schoolwork related

Very little F/LOSS awareness

What if? Ethical Problems!

[Context and origins]

3 > 4 teachers (voluntary basis)
4 > 5 PCs in a small room

Dissemination
Training
Support
Production

[Free as in Libre]

Not Freeware or Open Source

Freedom to run, copy, distribute, study, change and improve the software (FSF, 2012).

F0 to run the program for any purpose.

F1 to study how the program works and change it to make it do what you wish.

F2 to redistribute copies.

F3 to distribute copies of your modified versions to others.

[Free as in Libre]

Free Software and **Free Culture** are the natural result of an ethical choice towards a society and culture based on the free exchange of ideas and creativity, on freedom and sharing. They stand for an ecosystem that refuses the domination of the artificial barriers that benefit only a few.

[Free as in Libre]

- > Values of sharing and collaboration
- > Political and social responsibility
- > Quality of already available Libre Software
- > Financial savings

[Dissemination]

Presentations

Events

Website + Web 2.0

Room

[Training]

in-house

- > Central tenet of our activities.
- > Over 55 workshops (3-6h)
- > Diverse focus (more arts), contexts and softwares.

outside

[Training]

[Training]

Skills transfer: between students, between different programs, between different school levels

Building know-how: new skills at different school levels, not only F/LOSS related

New attitudes: continuous learning, software agnostic, collaboration, discovery and autonomous learning, internet and virtual communities

[Support]

EVTUX

Software installation

Edubuntu at Early Childhood

USB pens

[Support]

Since 2008/2009, 36% (39) of all final projects of the Arts and Multimedia graduate program (108) are developed with F/LOSS.

[Support]

14.8% (16) are short animation movies.

- Renderfarm and Libre animation
librepipeline.animaxionstudioz.com
www.animaxionstudioz.com

[Production]

Documentation

Action-coding

StudiozCollabPress
Ottographer
WebMizer
ProDISC
Festivalz

Research

Education

Arts

Free Software for Libre 3D Animation
Using Free Software is a statement about the world we live in and how we choose to live in it.

Infrastructure

OPERATING SYSTEM

- [Debian](#)
- [Fedora](#)
- [Linux Mint](#)
- [Ubuntu](#)
- [Ubuntu Studio](#)

PROJECT MANAGEMENT

- [GanttProject](#)
- [Plan](#)
- [Planner](#)
- [TaskJuggler](#)

BUDGET AND FINANCES

- [Buddi](#)
- [GnuCash](#)
- [Grisbi](#)
- [KMyMoney](#)

PRODUCTION/ASSET MANAGEMENT

- [Blender-aid](#)
- [Git](#)
- [Helga](#)
- [MediaGoblin](#)
- [OpenPipeline](#)
- [Stalker](#)
- [oyProjectManager](#)
- [SparkleShare](#)
- [StudiozCollabPress](#)
- [Subversion](#)

TACTIC

IMAGE MANAGEMENT

- [digiKam](#)
- [F-Spot](#)
- [Gallery](#)
- [Geeqie](#)
- [Gwenview](#)
- [KPhotoAlbum](#)
- [KSquirrel](#)
- [MediaGoblin](#)
- [Piwigo](#)
- [Shotwell](#)

FILE FORMATS

- [Alembic](#)
- [COLLADA](#)

Pre-production

IDEA & CONCEPT

- [Dia](#)
- [Flow](#)
- [FreeMind](#)
- [LibreOffice](#)
- [OpenOffice](#)
- [Visual Understanding Environment](#)

SCRIPT

- [Celtx](#)
- [LibOScreenplay](#)
- [Screenwright\(R\)](#)
- [Storybook](#)
- [Trelby](#)

STORYBOARD

- [Animix](#)
- [Celtx](#)
- [GIMP](#)
- [Krita](#)

CONCEPT ART

- [Alchemy](#)
- [Agave](#)
- [GIMP Paint Studio](#)
- [gpick](#)
- [MyPaint](#)
- [Krita](#)

Production

3D MODELING

- [Arbaro](#)
- [Art of Illusion](#)
- [Ayam](#)
- [Blender](#)
- [CanTree](#)
- [Insight3D](#)
- [K-3D](#)
- [Lithosphere](#)
- [MakeHuman](#)
- [MakerScanner](#)
- [MeshLab](#)
- [Misfit Model 3D](#)
- [OpenFX](#)
- [Picogen](#)
- [Seamless3d](#)
- [TopMod](#)
- [Wings 3D](#)

RIGGING

- [Art of Illusion](#)
- [Blender](#)
- [OpenFX](#)

LAYOUT

- [Art of Illusion](#)
- [Blender](#)
- [OpenFX](#)

ANIMATION

- [Art of Illusion](#)
- [Blender](#)
- [BVHplay](#)
- [Helix](#)
- [JLipSync](#)
- [OpenFX](#)
- [Papagayo](#)
- [QAvimator](#)

SHADING

- [Art of Illusion](#)
- [Blender](#)
- [OpenFX](#)
- [Open Shading Language](#)

TEXTURES

- [Blender](#)

Post-production

PAINT FIX / RETOUCH

- [CinePaint](#)
- [DJV Imaging](#)
- [Duke](#)
- [GIMP](#)
- [Hugin](#)
- [ImageMagick](#)
- [Krita](#)

VIDEO EDITING

- [Blender](#)
- [Cinelerra](#)
- [EKD](#)
- [FFmpeg](#)
- [Kdenlive](#)
- [Kino](#)
- [LiVES](#)
- [Lumiera](#)
- [Open Movie Editor](#)
- [OpenShot](#)
- [PiTiVi](#)
- [Shotcut](#)
- [slowmoVideo](#)

AUDIO EDITING

- [Ardour](#)
- [Audacity](#)
- [FluidSynth](#)
- [Hydrogen](#)
- [Jokosher](#)
- [LMMS](#)
- [MusE](#)
- [Open Octave](#)
- [Qtractor](#)
- [Rosegarden](#)
- [ReZound](#)
- [Traverso DAW](#)
- [ZynAddSubFX](#)

Distribution

CINEMA

- [Open Cinema Tools](#)
- [OpenDCP](#)

DVD

- [2ManDVD](#)
- [Bombono](#)
- [DeVeDe](#)
- [DVDAuthor](#)
- [DVD Styler](#)
- ['Q' DVD-Author](#)
- [Tovid](#)

WEB

- [Drupal](#)
- [WordPress](#)

OTHER USEFUL

- [ColorTribe](#)
- [darktable](#)
- [FontForge](#)
- [Gnome Subtitles](#)
- [LightZone](#)
- [RawTherapee](#)
- [Scribus](#)

[SWOT]

Strengths

- Mutual Support (7)
- Training (6)
- Ethics (5)
- On-site support (5)
- Know-how (4)
- Innovation, novelty (4)
- Learning reciprocity (4)
- Team functioning (3)
- No costs (3)
- Open to community (2)

- Low visibility (6)
- Resources (5) [Space (4)]
- Team functioning (4)
- ESEV confined (3)
- Irregular activity (2)

Weaknesses

35 people identified (23) | Online and anonymously

Opportunities

- Growing interest (4) [Crisis (2)]
- Partnerships (5)
- Software Quality (3)
- Public beyond school (3)
- Schools (3)
- Businesses (3)

- Indifference (5)
- Lack of available resources (4)
- Ignorance (3)
- Prejudice (2)
- Marketing (2)

Threats

[Tomorrow? Today!]

Policy making
More colleagues & courses
Software pipelines

Physical space
New hardware
Web server (Q&A,
renderfarm, plagiarism,
Zotero, mediagoblin, etc.)

(former) Student > student
Bring experts
Smaller, more often
More Education

Python & OSL coding
3D animation movie
Documentation
More research

Partnerships

Public beyond school

Free Software is a matter of liberty, not price. Using Free Software is a statement about the world we live in and how we choose to live in it.

openlab.esev.ipv.pt
nafergo.intervir.net

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 3.0 Unported License. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0>

IMAGES

Screen 2: adapted from Google Maps

Screen 4: adapted from "organize!" by worker (<http://openclipart.org/detail/102679/organize!-by-worker>)

Screen 5: "Heckert GNU white" by Anomie (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Heckert_GNU_white.svg) & "Tux" by Tene (<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Tux.png>)

Screen 6: composition based on "crashing wave" by johnny automatic (http://openclipart.org/detail/3166/crashing-wave-by-johnny_automatic), "comic characters: flag" by nicubuntu (<http://openclipart.org/detail/21872/comic-characters:-flag-by-nicubunu>), "free software gang" (<http://www.fsf.org/working-together/gang>) and organization logos

Screen 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15: OpenLab ESEV image archive

Screen 19: nafergo